

Taming the Oligopolists in the Shadows: The Big Four and the Governance of Global Value Chains

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Summary

1. The Big Four accounting firms (Deloitte, PwC, EY, KPMG) play a central yet underexamined role in shaping global production. Their influence extends far beyond auditing and tax services, coordinating and restructuring Global Value Chains (GVCs) across industries and geographies.
2. Their power is multidimensional, exercised through market dominance (bargaining power), regulatory influence (institutional power), professional culture and norms (demonstrative power), and the global diffusion of business practices (constitutive power).
3. These firms function as ‘one-stop-shops’, bundling legal, financial, and strategic services for multinational corporations, while also embedding themselves into public institutions and policy frameworks through lobbying and advisory roles.
4. Policy responses must focus on rebuilding public-sector capabilities and introducing stricter regulatory frameworks to reduce dependency, enhance transparency, and mitigate conflicts of interest in the operation of these powerful actors.

1. Introduction

The **Big Four** - Deloitte, PwC, EY, and KPMG - are often seen as global accounting firms with a broad portfolio of services. However, their role in the global economy is far more expansive and influential. Over time, the Big Four, have expanded their services from **audit, accountancy, tax and law** to **strategy consulting, IT transformation and advisory** on securities issuance and M&As. Today, they resemble a ‘**one-stopshop**’ (Greenwood,

Suddaby, and Hinings 2002) for corporate customers, governments and public-sector entities, rather than audit firms. With globalization and the establishment of **international accounting standards** (Perry and Nölke 2006), the Big Four have grown in size. In 2019, they employed **over 1 million people** in **2711 offices** worldwide, making combined gross revenue over **\$155 billion**.

This policy brief - based on the research findings of Iliopoulos & Wójcik (2024) - highlights how these firms function not just as

service providers but as **key coordinators** and **power brokers** in the global value chains (GVCs) that structure modern production and trade.

In an increasingly **service-driven** global economy, the Big Four are central players, not only supporting firms' participation in Global Value Chains (GVCs) but also shaping their structure, governance, and norms. Their influence extends across regulatory, institutional, and operational domains, often blurring the line between private service provision and public economic governance.

2. Methodology and Data

This research employs a **mixed-methods approach**, combining:

- **Quantitative data:** annual reports, corporate websites, industry publications, news articles, and think tank reports.
- **Qualitative data:** 16 in-depth interviews with senior executives of the Big Four and two non-Big Four firms, as part of a larger dataset of 200+ interviews across major economies.

The analysis draws on a framework of power conceptualization, which categorizes power into four types: **bargaining**, **institutional**, **demonstrative**, and **constitutive**. In that way, they capture the multifaceted ways in which power is exercised in GVCs.

Their typology distinguishes between the **main actors** that possess and exercise power and the **transmission mechanisms**, through which power is spread and is **dynamic** as it allows for one type of power to transform into another.

Bargaining power is the most common aspect of power found in political economy usually referring to the firm-to-firm (or more

generally to actor-to-actor) relationships. It is based on the resources and structural characteristics of the firm actors and can be operationalized by market concentration ratios, barriers to entry and economies of scale, scope and network. The second type – **institutional power** – is exercised by formal collectives, such as business associations and states, to design and establish worldwide regulations, rules and standards. **Demonstrative power** focuses on how actors exercise power through the transmission of requirements, inducing imitation of actions, products, tastes and preferences. Finally, **constitutive power** emerges from the uncoordinated, but collective actions of individuals and collectives, concerning the establishment of norms and best practices.

3. The Multiplicity of Power of the Big Four

The multiple dimensions in which the power of the Big Four is manifested and exercised through and within GVC, according to the DPS power typology are depicted in Figure 1, and elaborated below:

1. Bargaining Power

- The Big Four dominate auditing and consultancy markets, creating near-oligopolistic structures.
- Their scale, global networks, and integration of services enable them to offer "one-stop-shop" solutions that no other firm can match.
- They help firms enter, finance, and manage participation in GVCs—often acting as indispensable intermediaries.

2. Institutional Power

- Through professional associations (e.g., IFRS, IASB) and lobbying, the

Big Four influence global standard-setting and national regulations.

- They are active participants in EU and U.S. policy debates, including tax reform and sustainability reporting, often shaping rules that govern their own sectors.

3. Demonstrative Power

- Their global prestige and employee training pipelines shape corporate and governmental practices, particularly in accounting, audit, and governance.
- "Revolving doors" between the Big Four and government agencies reinforce their influence and institutional alignment.

4. Constitutive Power

- Beyond formal channels, the Big Four help entrench a global business culture rooted in auditability, outsourcing, and financialization.
- They promote resilience, climate adaptation, and digital transformation strategies—often becoming architects of new markets, like ESG services and carbon accounting.

4. Policy Implications

The extraordinary concentration of power in the Big Four presents challenges for accountability, market competition, and public governance. For instance, the highly concentrated market of consulting, auditing and tax services globally, as well as the magnitude of the economies of scale, scope and network of the Big Four, have rendered them extremely powerful in terms of bargaining power. Yet another element enhancing their bargaining position is the intricate relationship they nurture with the

world of finance. Because the Big Four have expanded their repertoire of services to financial markets, they have become 'obligatory passage points' in global financial networks, assisting capital provision to firms.

Adding to the bargaining power of the Big Four their role in promoting political, institutional and regulatory coherence in global economic transactions, particularly in relation to governance and reporting standards, through global professional and business associations, like the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), we end up with tremendous institutional power. Last but not least, their demonstrative and constitutive power regarding the professional and audit culture, formal and informal norms and cultural gravitas, channelled through the professional trajectories of employees and executives and their influence over public debates, accounting education, brand names, the professionalization of economic activities and the imposition of a globalized outsourced/offshored and highly financialized, business model. Two core policy recommendations emerge:

Rebuild Public Capacity

- Governments must **reduce dependency** on the Big Four by reinvesting in internal expertise and public-sector capabilities.
- Strengthening **in-house knowledge** and reducing reliance on outsourced consultancy can counteract the "**infantilization**" of public institutions (see Mazzucato & Collington, 2024).

Enforce Stronger Regulation and Transparency

- Introduce stricter rules to **separate auditing and consultancy** services to avoid conflicts of interest.
- Mandate greater transparency in lobbying activities, client disclosures, and consultancy contracts with public entities.

These reforms are essential to address power asymmetries, ensure market integrity, and promote a more transparent and democratic global economic order.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

References

Dallas, M. P., Ponte, S., & Sturgeon, T. J. (2019). Power in global value chains. *Review of International Political Economy*, 26(4), 666–694.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290.2019.1608284>

Greenwood, R., Suddaby, R., & Hinings, C. R. (2002). Theorizing Change: The Role of Professional Associations in the Transformation of Institutionalized Fields. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 45(1), 58–80.

Iliopoulos, P. (Takis), & Wójcik, D. (2025). The Big Four: Multiple Functions and Power in Global Value Chains. *Global*

Networks, 25(1), e12507.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/glob.12507>

Mazzucato, M., & Collington, R. (2024). *The Big Con: How the Consulting Industry Weakens our Businesses, Infantilizes our Governments and Warps our Economics*. Penguin Books.

Perry, J., & Nölke, A. (2006). The political economy of International Accounting Standards. *Review of International Political Economy*, 13(4), 559–586.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290600839790>

Figures

		Transmission Mechanisms	
		Direct	Diffuse
Arena of Actors	Dyadic	<p><i>Bargaining Power</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through actor-to-actor relationships. • Multidisciplinary Practice Firms (MPFs) acting as 'one-stop-shops' and 'body-shops', for private and public clients. • Exerting oligopolistic power in the market, built on economies of scale, scope and networks. 	<p><i>Demonstrative Power</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through former, current and future employees. • Ticket to the upper middle-class and the ladder for future corporate executives. • Revolving doors for government positions.
	Collective	<p><i>Institutional Power</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through multi-level standard-setting and lobbying activities. • Key players in IFRS, IASB, and ACCA shaping the standards of accounting, audit, and financial management. • Players in GFMA and ISDA, contributing to broader financial sector lobbying. 	<p><i>Constitutive Power</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through generalisation of norms and best practices. • Audit culture and financialized business models. • Anglo-American expertise and hegemony.

FIGURE 1 | Typology of power of the Big Four. ACCA, Association of Chartered Certified Accountants; IFRS, International Financial Reporting Standards; IASB, International Accounting Standards Board. *Source:* Own Illustration. Adapted from Dallas, Ponte, and Sturgeon (2019, 673) and modified by the authors.

Further Information:

Iliopoulos, P. (Takis), & Wójcik, D. (2025). The Big Four: Multiple Functions and Power in Global Value Chains. *Global Networks*, 25(1), e12507. <https://doi.org/10.1111/glob.12507>

Funded by the European Union

DemoTrans is funded by the European Union (Horizon Europe Framework, Grant Number 101059288). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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